

A REVIEW OF FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE GROWTH AND YIELD OF SWEET POTATO UNDER FIELD CONDITION

By

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Abstract

Crop production under field conditions is the goal in most agricultural experiments. The factors that influence the growth and yield of sweet potato under field conditions were reviewed in this paper. Understanding of these factors is very foundational and critical to the enhancement of the yield of the crop. There are factors that are inherent to the crop, while others are external, all of which are subject to scientific engineering and cultural manipulation to increase tuber yield. Soil conditions are significant to the growth and yield and there is the need for a prior determination of the nutrient status of the soil before planting is done. The site of production too needs to be in the ecological zone to which the crop is naturally adapted. The need to enhance the factors that promote tuber yield is emphasized, while placement method for less soluble fertilizers, provision of vine supports or stakes, increasing source and sink capacities, good pests and disease management, wider use of sweet potato, bridging the gap between the crop and tuber crops as well as improved post-harvest management are advocated.

INTRODUCTION

In experimental agriculture, crops can be grown in the green house under which the growth conditions are well controlled. The performance of crops under such a condition is never the same with what obtains under field conditions. In the field, crops are exposed to the hazard of edaphic or soil factors as well as unpredictable climatic conditions. Therefore, a review of the factors that affect the growth and yield

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of sweet potato under field conditions is not out of place. Sweet potato *Ipomoea batatas* (L.) Lam) belongs to the family Convulaceae and it is a crop that is widely grown in many parts of the tropical and sub-tropical regions. It grows best on sandy loam soils with good drainage and a pH range of 5.6-6.6. Rainfall of 75-100cm per annum and temperatures above 24°C are considered adequate for the crop, Cobley, (1976). Each plant produces only a few number of tubers and as plant population per hectare increases, the number of tubers per plant decreases; the mean weight per tuber decreases, and the yield per plant also decreases (Enyi; 1977).

Sweet potato is a high energy producing crop and it is one of the most promising food crops that can meet the energy requirement of the people in the tropics. Apart from its importance as human food, sweet potato provides animal feed and raw materials for industries. It requires relatively little attention and its production costs are low compared with some other field crops. It has very high-solar energy fixing efficiency among food crops, because of its tremendous capacity to produce dry mater (DM) for a long period of time.

In Nigeria, sweet potato is comparatively not as popular as other root and tuber crops like cassava, cocoyam and yam. Yet in some localities; it is a cultural crop in the sense that, it is deeply associated with the culture of the people that consume it in different forms. Haynes and Wholey (1971), observed that the number of tubers per plant can range from 0-13 and the weight of tubers per plant, can range from 10-872g. These investigators attributed the variation in the number and yield of tubers to factors external to the crop such as soil, management practices, climatic conditions, as well as inherent factors; including type of planting material. Furthermore, Haynes (1970), was able to identify some general and regional problems of sweet potato production. Among the general problems are the use of inappropriate planting materials in particular production systems and in the high degrees of variability of the sweet potato crop itself. The regional problems according to Haynes, are related to environmental conditions, the level of technology under which the crop is grown and the agronomic practices incorporated into the production system.

Sweet potato characteristically is a heavy utilizer of soil nutrients in the light of its morphology, especially the elaborate foliage cover that is a consequence of its

creeping vines. Adventitious roots develop at the nodes and the tendency of tuberization at the upper nodes is equally high. The effects of Nitrogen (N) and Potassium (K) on the growth and yield of sweet potato have been a major field of interest to many investigators. Duncan, Scott and Stark (1958), and Godfrey-Sam-Aggrey (1974), concluded that, fertilizers containing higher K rates and an N/K ratio of 3:4 gave maximum tuber yields. Generally, it is known that the response of sweet potato to fertilizer application depends on the soil type, the environment and the cultivar grown. In addition, it is known that Phosphorus (P) improves the water use efficiency (WUE) of crops and plays a principal role in energy transfer and storage as a constituent of Nicotinamide Adenosine Dinucleotide Phosphate (NADP) as well as Adenosine Triphosphate (ATP); Tisdale and Nelson, (1975), Tombesi, Cale and Tiborne (1969), Rendle and Kang, (1977). Sweet potato is a high energy producing crop and still, its response to added phosphate fertilizer has not been very consistent which may as well be the factor of native soil P. Rendle and Kang (1977), reported that P response of sweet potato has been observed to be small or outrightly insignificant. In their pot experiment, they could not obtain a decisive response of sweet potato to added P. Even at this, the conditions of pot experiment are different from what is obtained under field conditions. Similarly, Constantin, Jones and Hernandez (1977), reported that considerable research has been directed towards the effects of K and P fertilization on the yield, shape, grade and vine growth of sweet potatoes. However, some controversy exists as to the response of sweet potato to P fertilization; probably due to the effects of inherent soil P. Thus, different factors profoundly influence the growth, development and yield of sweet potato under field conditions. Enhancement of these factors, when so identified will go a long way to promote the tuber yield (both in quality and quantity) of sweet potato.

GENERAL REVIEW

The crop plant is a biological system that is influenced negatively or positively by a number of internal as well as external factors. The preponderance of

those factors that enhance the balanced growth and development of any crop is the major focus in agronomy. When they are naturally present; they are to be maintained and where not; they have to be supplied.

One of the fundamental factors that affect the growth and the yield of sweet potato is the level of **Native Soil Nutrients** (NSN). Those that affect the performance of sweet potato as a crop, fall into the categories of major and minor nutrients. It is a well known fact that, potassium (K) affects tuberous root yield most. It affects the dry matter (DM) production by increasing net Photosynthetic activity of a given leaf area (LA). The concept of native soil nutrients bothers on what a land has through natural processes of nitrification, nitrogen fixation, decomposition, mineralization and nutrient recycling. An uninterrupted land has a stable ecosystem, in which the soil medium and nutrients are at an equilibrium, until such a time of deforestation that agricultural activities entail. A fertile and productive soil therefore will encourage good growth and yield of sweet potato. Root and tuber crops are at home in such Nigerian ecological areas as the forest zone and to some extent the guinea savanna zone, because of the crop growth promoting levels of the native soil nutrients.

Plant structure is another pertinent factor influencing the field performance of sweet potato. Plant structure has to do with the morphological arrangement of the various components of the shoot system. The leaves as the principal organ of photosynthetic activities may be fully or partially exposed to absorb sunlight energy, that can be converted to assimilates. Sweet potato crop has a high photosynthetic capacity per unit of leaf area (LA) but mutual shading occurs, because of a leaf arrangement which causes poor sunlight penetration. Consequently, the net assimilation rate (NAR) decreases with an increase of leaf area index (LAI) in natural populations; Ramanujam and Indira, (1979); Lowe and Wilson, (1975), Enyi (1977). Thus Hahn (1977), expressed that, the favourable external conditions for high yield are those which promote nutrient absorption, improve light penetration in natural populations, increase net photosynthetic activity and improved formation and enlargement of tuberous roots.

Planting material is what is used to establish a new plant. It may be seed (sexual propagation) or a cutting (vegetative) as the case may be. For the sweet potato crop; cuttings used for propagation can be from the tuber or the vines. This is where sweet potato has a double honour over such associates as yam and cassava. While yam can only be propagated in commercial quantities by cutting the tubers into setts, cassava can only be propagated by stem cuttings in commercial production. For breeding purposes; seeds are used for propagation in yam and cassava Onwueme; (1970). In sweet potato, the effect of cutting lengths on tuber yields had been investigated. Godfrey-Sam-Aggrey (1974), reported that the longer the cutting lengths, the higher the yields and that, the vine/tuber ratio is inversely proportional to tuber yield. Availability of planting material is really a problem in sweet potato production. As planting date normally coincides with the raining season period; it is not as easy to have stored the vines for propagation purposes from the harvest of the previous crop. The probable option is to store some tubers for future multiplication purposes, Ajiboye (1984). This approach may not be economical since the tubers serve as food and raw materials for industries.

Following the conclusions of other workers that, the mutual shading that results from excessive leaf production in sweet potato tends to reduce tuber yields, some investigators attempted the agronomic practice of **staking** for better foliage display. Gollifer (1973), established that staking could significantly increase the yield of tubers and Haynes and Wholey (1971), also suggested that, staking might be expected to improve the foliage display of a high vine producing cultivar of sweet potato. Ajiboye (1984), also observed the tendency of tuber proliferation in an unstaked plot of sweet potato. Due to the creeping nature of the vines; the upper nodes develop adventitious roots among which a few of them get modified into tubers. This development led to increase in the number of tubers per plant, but gross reduction in the size of the tubers or marketable tubers. This is not profitable to the farmers on the field. Therefore, as tasking as staking may be in sweet potato production; it is a worthwhile adventure; after all, yam producers take up the

challenge of providing stakes on their yam fields.

Vine training is an agronomic practice that is closely related to staking. It is an effort in which the vines are kept to the stakes provided; instead of their trailing on the ground. Training is also a method of altering the leaf display of sweet potato. Thus, Chapman and Cowling (1965), concluded that, the yield of tubers increased significantly as a result of the training of the vines on wire-mesh and it also turned a negative effect of Nitrogen on tuber yield to a positive one. In addition it was established that leaf area duration (LAD) was promoted with the provision of the wire mesh. Therefore, to these investigators, staking and vine training are worthwhile efforts in sweet potato production and they should be adopted by the producers.

The effects of **added nutrients** on the growth and yield of sweet potato have been a major field of interest to many investigators. Godfrey-Sam-Aggrey (1976), concluded that fertilizers containing higher K rates and a N/K ratio of 3:4 gave maximum tuber and low vine yields with low vine/tuber ratio on intensively cropped areas. Duncan *et al* (1958), had also reported a high K requirement of sweet potato. Generally, variation in tuber yield in root crop cultivars may be due to either the differences in the number of tubers per plant, differences in the size of tuber or to both factors. Lowe and Wilson (1975), noted that, there was a significant positive correlation between these yield components and total tuber yield in sweet potato cultivars. Whereas, cultivars with lower tuber numbers usually produced a higher percentage of marketable tubers. There is a distinction between tuber initiation and tuber development as both can be affected by the nutrients status of the soil. Thus, Wilson (1973), concluded that the onset of early tuber growth was inversely related to levels of N supply. It was therefore observed that high levels of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ supply retarded early tuber growth due to promotion of vegetative growth. Furthermore Kay (1973), expressed that response of sweet potato to the application of fertilizers seems to be very much influenced by the cultivars and climatic conditions. It was observed that, apart from high levels of N, P and K; sweet potato requires some micronutrients

such as Boron, Calcium and Magnesium for good growth and optimal yield.

Generally, responses of sweet potato to added nutrients depend on a number of environmental factors; particularly the varying amounts of soil nutrients and organic matter (OM) contents Kang (1973), reported that, where bush burning is a cultural practice, substantial amount of available P is deposited by the ashes. Similarly, Oko and Agboola (1976), noticed that when soil organic matter is three (3) percent or more, the available P released from organic matter decomposition and mineralization is substantial, and it should be taken into consideration when making fertilizer recommendations. Osiname (1979), also concluded that small annual P application may be preferable to occasional large dressings. The fact that, less than fifty percent (50%) of the applied P is utilized by the first target crop has been established. Thomas and Hanway (1968), stated that only 15-25 percent of the added P is used by the crop in the year of application. In addition, Kilmer and Webb (1968), reported that the effectiveness of Phosphate fertilizers is dependent upon the chemical and physical characteristics of the fertilizer, rate and method of application, soil and climatic conditions under which the crop is grown as well as the crop characteristics. The response of sweet potato to P application has generally been reported to be insignificant, Rendle and Kang (1977).

The degree of root system development determines, to a large extent the utilization of added P. Ahn (1970), observed that phosphate ions do not move very far in the soil and as such, they have to be very close to the plant root for easy absorption. Consequently, it is the root that has to go to the anions; in which case, adequate phosphate absorption depends very much on the extent of plant root development. The root tips move through the soil as the root system expands, exploring new soil areas. Thus the amount of phosphate ions absorbed depends largely on the extent of the root systems and the total volume of soil which they explore. This is why placement method of application is most preferable for phosphate fertilizers that are less water soluble, thereby limiting their contact with soil volume. The beneficial effect of placed applications as compared with broadcast treatments has been well

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documented by a number of authors such as Prummel (1957), Ryan (1962), Reith (1972). Furthermore, some residual effects of phosphate fertilizers have been reported indicating that, some of the fixed phosphate becomes available again to benefit subsequent crops. Russell (1973), gave progressive responses to a single application of about 80kgP/ha applied as superphosphate in four years. The increases obtained in each of the subsequent years were residual responses.

Earlier Ahn (1970), stated that, those soils that have a long history of cultivation and phosphate addition have sometimes ceased to respond to additional applications because of the progressively greater accumulations of added phosphate they contain. Constantin *et al* (1977), similarly reported that on the effects of K and P fertilization on the yield, shape, grade and vine development of sweet potato; controversy exists as to the response to P probably due to the effects of inherent or native soil P.

The fact that, sweet potato is a great utilizer of K was noticed as far back as 1950 by Scott. He observed that, the percentage of K in sweet potato vines decreased during the period of tuber bulking and its accumulation in the tuber, practically accounted for all of the K uptake during the last two months of the growing season. In addition, Hammett and Miller (1982), observed that NH_4NO_3 and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ were equivalent in influence on the tuber quality at harvest and storage of sweet potato. While they also noticed that, an increase in K rate from 70 to 280kg/ha reduced root dry matter content. Duncan *et al* (1958), also reported that, in using K_2O and K_2SO_4 as sources of K fertilization for sweet potato; total yields were influenced by rates rather than the sources of potash. Dry matter (DM) content decreased with increased rate of potash application in all cases while K content of sweet potato increased as the rate of potash application increased.

Sweet potato has both fibrous and tuberous roots. The process of assimilate deposition leading to the development of tuberous roots is called tuberization while the increase in the size of the tubers is termed bulking. Tuber yield is a product of both the rate of bulking and duration of bulking, Enyi (1977). The percentage of total

assimilates diverted into the vine also counts in the tuber yield of sweet potato and therefore, Godfrey-San-Aggrey (1974) found that, the lower the vine/tuber ratio, the higher the tuber yield. It was established that tuber yield increased linearly with increase in root weight to stem weight ratios. Similarly, comparing eight (8) sweet potato cultivars in 1977; Enyi was of the opinion that, the higher yielding cultivars bulked the much faster than the others and stated further that, a pulling function of photosynthates is necessary for tuberous root growth. Those cultivars that possess inherent properties for attracting considerable quantities of the photosynthates for the development of the tubers yielded higher. In addition, Enyi submitted that bulking rate and tuber weight are positively correlated with tuber yield, while the percentage dry matter diverted into the vine is negatively correlated with tuber yield.

Source and sink are two physiological terminologies that have much bearing with the yield of any crop. The term source refers to the centre where assimilates are produced while the sink is the venue or organ of assimilate deposition. The sink also serves as the organ of storage whose capacity can be enhanced. However an increase in one without a corresponding increase in the other will have no positive effect on the yield. Consequently, Hahn (1977), reported that, the economic yield of sweet potato may be limited by either photosynthetic source potential or tuberous root sink capacity. Hahn observed that, cultivars with large sink capacities showed greater responses of sink to source than the varieties with poor sink capacities. The cultivars with the greater source potential showed the greatest response of source to sink. It was also observed that, in a cultivar that has a large vine; the top growth represents a more active sink which competes with the root for assimilate than in the other cultivars and in part contributes to the root-sink limitation of the cultivar. Thus, while an active source coupled to a large root-sink capacity is desirable; the source component should not be too active as a competitive sink.

Like any other field crop, there are **parameters** that determine the yield of sweet potato otherwise called yield determinants. In this regard, Wilson (1970), reported that the ultimate determinants of total sweet potato tuber yield are tuber

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weight (TW) and tuber number (TN) per plant. Parameters of sweet potato tuberization are therefore defined as those aspects of the process of tuberization that in the course of tuber development affect either the number or size of tubers at harvest. Wilson *et al* (1969), proposed the following parameters of tuberization:-

- PTI, Potential Tuberization Index; meaning the number of roots per plant capable of developing into tubers.
- PTI, Percentage Tuberization Index; meaning the percentage of the roots that initiate and develop tubers.
- TNPP, Tuber number per plant.
- TWPP, Tuber weight per plant.

These parameters determine the pattern of yield variation among different sweet potato cultivars, (Wilson; 1970). Enhancement of these yield parameters is the focus of the agronomists, plant breeders as well as crop physiologists such that, the ultimate goal of all production efforts that is; the yield can be realised.

The attacks of **pests** and **diseases** are a common occurrence in crop production principles and practices. Effective control or management of these biotic agents is the major focus of crop protection studies. A number of pests and diseases are known to plague the sweet potato crop, the result of which is gross yield reduction. Tanaka and Sekioka (1976), reported that the insects that most commonly attack sweet potato are weevils, stem borers and red spider mites. While the major disease of the crop is leaf scab caused by *Sphaceloma batatas*. Thus Mukiibi (1976), reported that, the sweet potato mosaic virus disease (MVD) caused a 57% reduction in yield both in terms of the weight and the number of root tubers. Hahn (1979), also observed that the yield of fresh tubers was reduced by 78 percent in plants showing Sweet Potato Virus Disease (SPVD) symptoms.

Storage problem is one of the greatest challenges in sweet potato industry. Soon after harvest; except proper curing is done, the tuber may begin to decay with much dry matter and moisture losses. Curing can be in form of slicing the tubers, and

sun-drying the pieces for the purpose of storage. Losses may account for up to 50% or more if care is not taken. One of the recently identified methods to check these losses is the storage of the tubers under moderate low oxygen content. Chang and Kays (1981), concluded that, the respiratory rates of roots stored at oxygen concentrations of 5-15% were lower than those of roots at 20% oxygen. Under these conditions, biochemical transformation of carbohydrates to a reducing sugar and dextrin with sucrose being synthesized from the reducing sugar is considerably reduced.

CONCLUSION

Ecological zones with their characteristic features carry different crops in the substitution by elimination that cropping activity suggests. The land is cleared in the art of deforestation, while cropping is in actual fact a form of afforestation. Distribution of crops follows the pattern of natural vegetation. While cereals and grain legumes are at home in the savanna; roots, tubers and tree crops are roundly suited for the forest zone. Root and tuber crops constitute the staple food of most people in the tropics. It is only wise for people of a particular zone to promote the production of those crops that are naturally adapted to such zones. Consequently, sweet potato as a root crop of the tropics is a crop that has a natural acceptability to Southern Nigeria as well as the relatively wetter parts of Northern Nigeria. The crop is a source of human food, animal feed as well as a raw material for local industries. There are a number of factors that influence the growth and tuber yield of the crop ranging from edaphic, climatic, cultural to general management. Positive manipulation of these factors will definitely promote the yield of the crop and such can widen its horizon and greater geographical spread as well as acceptability. Growing crops that are native to our country is more reasonable, acceptable and realistic than unadvised adventure into the production of crops like wheat that some States had embarked upon in our most recent past and yet sweet potato is a Nigerian native crop.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Indiscriminate use of fertilizers on sweet potato field should be avoided.
2. Knowledge of the levels of soil nutrients should remain a salient tool for fertilizer recommendations.
3. The application of less soluble fertilizers especially those of phosphate should be by placement or drilling method to minimize wastage.
4. Provision of stakes to crops with weak stems like sweet potato is a necessity to promote leaf display and sunlight penetration for the enhancement of photosynthetic activities.
5. Enhancement of source capacity must as of necessity, be accompanied by increased sink capacity to promote yield or harvest index.
6. Adequate pest and disease management has become imperative to promote the yield of sweet potato in Nigeria.
7. Exploration of a wider use of sweet potato by Nigerian food and chemical industries is of absolute necessity.
8. The gap between sweet potato on one hand versus yams, cocoyam and cassava on the other, should be bridged via publicity since they are all in the same agronomic group of crops.
9. Post harvest processing of sweet potato tubers for safe storage is advocated to encourage local producers.
10. The time is ripe for the National Bureau of Statistics to start capturing data on sweet potato as it has been done for yam, cassava and cocoyam, over the years.

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